

ASSESSMENT OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI COMMUNITY, YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS.

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ABSTRACT

Background: This research work was aimed at assessing the oral health problems of the elderly populace of Ikibiri community, Bayelsa State as well as determining possible solutions to these problems.

Method: A descriptive study design was carried out on 100 respondents comprising of elderly individuals of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State between the ages of 60 - 110 years. Interviewer - based questionnaires assessing the presence of specific oral health problems as well as delivery of oral health services were used as our instrument for data collection.

Results: Bleeding gums (52%), toothache (44%), and oral sores (42%) were found to be the major oral health problems being experienced by the population under study and these were mostly attributed to the absence of a dentist (95%), absence of a dental clinic (94%) as well as the absence of oral health education to the community (87%).

Conclusion: Oral health problems are undoubtedly present among the elderly individuals of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa LGA, Bayelsa State which was attributed to the absence of dental personnel, dental facilities and oral health education. It was however recommended that Ikibiri community be provided with dental personnel and facilities as well as the provision of oral health education to the entire populace of Ikibiri; which would indeed reduce the burden of oral health problems among the elderly in this community.

KEYWORDS: Oral health problems, Causes, Solutions

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INTRODUCTION

Oral health is a standard of health of the oral and related tissues which enables an individual to eat, speak and socialize without active disease, discomfort or embarrassment and which contributes to the general well being of an individual, thus preserving the highest levels of self esteem of such an individual, as there is increasing recognition that oral health has a significant impact on physical, social and psychological wellbeing of an individual. (Danfillo, 2009; Olusile, 2010; Saimadhavi et al, 2013). Generally, oral health in Africa has been characterized by low to very low caries prevalence and severity, inadequacy of oral health care personnel when matched with population needs, low priority given to oral health as well as poor working conditions. (Danfillo, 2009).

In Nigeria, there abounds a low level of oral health awareness, a high prevalence of periodontal disease leading to tooth loss which increases with age, very low to moderate prevalence of dental caries as well as the occurrence of other conditions such as oral cancers, dental fluorosis e.t.c. Nigeria also manifests an apparent lack of coordination for the provision of preventive dental services with little or no access to modern dental

treatment within her rural areas and therapeutic dental services mainly available in the urbanized areas with the occasional visits of dentists to the rural areas. (Akpata, 2004; Taiwo et al, 2004; Taiwo and Omokhodoin, 2006; Sofola, 2010). In addition, it has been reported that factors affecting the oral health of the elderly populace in India include almost non-existent or limited preventive dental care, grossly insufficient dental personnel, poverty, illiteracy as well as lack of social security. (Shah, 2001).

It has been reported that the elderly make-up an important part of the general population as a result of the concomitant increase of the elderly population which is largely due to increasing life expectancy in most parts of the world and this increasing life expectancy has been associated with better nourishment, hygiene and healthcare of the elderly populace. The world's population of those aged 60 years and above increases by about a million every month and that by the year 2035; it is projected that the elderly will constitute one in every four persons. (WHO, 2003; Owotade et al, 2005; Pesic, 2007). A number of surveys have reported significant oral health impairment as well as poor oral hygiene among the elderly especially among the institutionalized which has been attributed to several factors including age-related changes that affect the oral health. Likewise, older adults are more vulnerable to diseases of the oral cavity due to an increase in chronic conditions as well as physical and mental disabilities. Thus, old people are a peculiar group in terms of service provision. (Owotade et al, 2005; Bhardwaj, 2012).

Oral diseases which the elderly are particularly prone to include root caries, attrition, attrition, missing teeth due to earlier neglect, edentulism, poor alveolar ridge quality, mucosal lesions, oral ulcerations/sores, dry mouth (xerostomia) amongst others including oral cancers whose incidence is highest in India, with 13.5% of all body cancers being oral cancers. Most of these diseases are indeed a sequelae of neglect in the early years of life of these individuals which includes poor knowledge of how to prevent oral diseases, tobacco smoking, consumption of cariogenic diets, betel nut chewing, to mention but a few. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Edwards and Kanjirath, 2010; Shah, 2001). The presence of these oral diseases as well as coexisting medical problems usually increases in magnitude the declining immunity associated with old age.

Due to poor systemic health, the elderly patient does not pay sufficient attention to oral health and it has indeed been reported that elderly people are least likely to seek dental care except in emergency situations as oral health is perceived to be a less important need when compared with physical health in general. Furthermore, financial constraints, lack of family support, misconceptions of dental treatment, low level of oral health awareness and transportation facilities adversely affect access to dental services when it concerns the elderly. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Owotade et al, 2005; Sofola, 2010). From studies carried out in the South-East Local Government Area in Ibadan, it was gathered that there was a high level of unmet dental needs as well as lack of perceived need among the elderly individuals from this area which thus contributed to their poor dental clinic attendance despite having good attitudes towards oral health. (Taiwo J.O. et al, 2007; Taiwo J.O. et al, 2012). In all these, reports State that experiences from developed countries show that the prevalence of chronic diseases and high levels of disability among the elderly and indeed for the entire populace can be reduced through health promotion and appropriate prevention strategies designed to improve quality of life. (Bhardwaj, 2012; Olushile, 2010; Sofola, 2010).

It has been observed that little or no reports exist concerning the oral health needs of the elderly populace in Ikibiri Community Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State amidst the fact that they are faced with different types of oral health problems of which most of them are not aware of thus the desire to identify the oral health needs and feasible strategies for solving them in this community. This study is significant in that it would provide pertinent information about the oral health problems of Ikibiri community as well as means that could be employed in controlling dental problems and promoting oral health and thus the general health of the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community, Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

METHODS

We employed a descriptive study design in determining the oral health problems of the elderly populace of Ikibiri community, Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Interviewer - based

questionnaires assessing the presence of specific oral health problems as well as delivery of oral health services were distributed among 100 respondents gotten by a convenience sampling technique comprising of elderly individuals of this community ranging between the ages of 60 - 110 years. Permission to carry out data collection was gotten from the Chairman of the Community Development Committee of Ikibiri Community and the decision by the respondents to be involved in this study was completely voluntary. Data gotten from the respondents was analyzed using the Epi Info 3.4.3 statistical software and the relationship among certain oral health problems was determined.

RESULTS

Altogether, 100 respondents participated in this study. The modal age group was between ages 60 – 70 years, n=56 (56%); 58% of the respondents were females and the major occupation the respondents were involved in was farming (60%). The demographic data of the respondents is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESPONDENTS

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. AGE			
• 60 – 70	56	56.00	45.70 – 65.90
• 71 – 80	25	25.00	16.90 – 34.70
• 81 – 90	15	15.00	8.60 – 23.50
• 91 – 100	3	3.00	0.60 – 8.50
• 101 – 110	1	1.00	0.00 – 5.40
2. GENDER			
• MALE	42	42.00	32.20 – 52.30
• FEMALE	58	58.00	47.70 – 67.80
3. OCCUPATION			
• CIVILSERVANT	13	13.00	7.10 – 21.20
• FARMER	60	60.00	49.70 – 69.70
• FISHING	11	11.00	5.6 – 18.80
• RETIRED	13	13.00	7.10 – 21.20
• SELF EMPLOYED	3	3.00	0.60 – 8.50
4. MARITAL STATUS			
• MARRIED	63	63.00	52.80 – 72.40
• DIVORCED	1	1.00	0.00 – 5.40
• SINGLE	4	4.00	1.10 – 9.90
• WIDOW	27	27.00	18.60 – 36.80
• WIDOWER	5	5.00	1.60 – 11.30
5. RELIGION			
• CHRISTIANITY	91	91.00	83.60 – 95.80
• ISLAM	1	1.00	0.00 – 5.40
• OTHERS	8	8.00	3.50 – 15.20

N= 100; AGE RANGE: 60 – 110; MODAL AGE GROUP: 60 - 70

ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS OF RESPONDENTS

In all, 52% of the respondents said they were experiencing bleeding gums, 44% were experiencing some form of tooth ache, 42% had sores/injuries in their mouths and 34% of the respondents had dry mouth (xerostomia). This is outlined in Table 2.

TABLE 2: ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS OF THE RESPONDENTS

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. BLEEDING GUMS	52	52.00	41.80 – 62.10
2. TOOTHACHE	44	44.00	34.10 – 54.30
3. SORES/ INJURIES IN THE MOUTH	42	42.00	32.20 – 52.30
4. DRY MOUTH	34	34.00	24.80 – 44.20

CAUSES OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI COMMUNITY

In our survey, it was gathered that the absence of a Dentist (95%), the absence of a dental clinic (94%) as well as the absence of oral health education were major causes of the oral health problems being experienced by the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community. This is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: CAUSES OF ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG THE ELDERLY POPULACE OF IKIBIRI

PARAMETER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (%)
1. ABSENCE OF A DENTIST	95	95.00	88.70 – 98.70
2. ABSENCE OF A DENTAL CLINIC	94	94.00	87.40 – 97.80
3. ABSENCE OF ORAL HEALTH EDUCATION	87	87.00	78.80 – 92.90

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRESENCE OF BLEEDING GUMS AS AN ORAL HEALTH PROBLEM AND THE PRESENCE OF OTHER ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

An interesting relationship was found to exist between the presence of bleeding gums and the presence of toothache and oral sores. It was observed that as the number of cases of bleeding gums were increasing, the number of cases of toothache also increased ($r=0.31$, $p\text{-value}=0.002$) and the number of cases of oral sores increased as well ($r=0.25$, $p\text{-value}=0.01$). This is outlined in Table 4.

TABLE 4: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE PRESENCE OF BLEEDING GUMS AS AN ORAL HEALTH PROBLEM AND THE PRESENCE OF OTHER ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

Variable	Correlation Coefficient	Standard Error	p-value
Toothache	0.305	0.094	0.001649*
Dry Mouth	0.093	0.101	0.360543
Oral Sores	0.253	0.096	0.010229"

p-value is set at <0.05

*Significant relationship between Bleeding gums and Toothache ($p=0.002$, $r=0.31$)

"Significant relationship between Bleeding gums and Sores in the mouth ($p=0.01$, $r=0.25$)

METHODS OF ORAL HYGIENE USED BY THE RESPONDENTS

Amongst the respondents, 51% use toothbrush to clean their mouths, 28% use chewing stick, 14% use only water to rinse their mouths, 4% use charcoal to clean their mouths, 2% use saltwater and 1% of the respondents

use sand as an oral hygiene method. The distribution of what the respondents use in maintaining their oral hygiene is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: METHODS OF ORAL HYGIENE USED BY RESPONDENTS

THE ACTION OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

Out of the total population of the respondents, 38% of the respondents went to the chemist to buy drugs to use in order to treat the problem, 28% of the respondents do nothing i.e. they do not do anything to treat themselves when they have oral health problems. 21% of the respondents treat themselves traditionally and only 13% visit the dentist to receive treatment when they have oral health problems. This is shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: THE ACTION OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS ORAL HEALTH PROBLEMS

DISCUSSION

An important criteria for successful aging apart from the availability of health promotion and appropriate prevention strategies designed to improve quality of life, is also the maintenance of a functional, natural and healthy dentition throughout life, including all the social and biologic benefits such as aesthetics, comfort, the ability to chew, taste and speak. As the elderly populace increases, there would be an increasing demand on dental services by such individuals. (Owotade et al, 2005).

From the results of this study, the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community certainly experience oral health problems. It was seen that the age group of 60 – 70 years had the highest population in this study and accounted for 56% of the respondents, this is in line with the findings of Owotade et al (2005). Majority of the respondents are farmers which accounted for 60.0% of the population, this is in line with the fact that the occupation of the people of Ikibiri community in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria is farming. 63.0% of the respondents are married and christians were accounted for the highest number of respondents. This may be due to the fact that the south – south region of Nigeria is dominated by Christianity.

The major oral health problem among the elderly in Ikibiri Community was bleeding gums (52.0%), which may be due to poor oral hygiene status (Akpata, 2004) as well as poor oral health education and awareness among the elderly populace of this community which agrees with the reports of Sofola (2010). 44% of the respondents had toothache as an oral health problem which may have been due to the lack of appropriate dental awareness, lack of dental health facilities as well as dentists in the community. Sores/injuries in the mouth were oral health problems affecting 42% of the respondents which may have been due to poor oral health practices. Dry mouth recorded a 34% occurrence among the respondents as an oral health problem and may be due to various medications being taken by the elderly in this community.

The possible causes of oral health problems among the elderly in Ikibiri community indicated that almost all of the respondents (95%) attributed it to the absence of a dentist. 94.0% of the respondents were of the opinion that the absence of a dental clinic was a major cause and a contributing factor to the prevalence of oral health problems in the community and 87.0% of the respondents agreed that the absence of oral health education was a cause of oral health problems in Ikibiri Community.

The elderly populace of Ikibiri Community had various practices when they had oral health problems, which included going to the chemist to buy drugs to use (38.0%), treating themselves with local herbs at home (21.0%), doing nothing (28.0%) and going to visit the dentist to obtain dental treatment at the State capital Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Furthermore, out of all the respondents, 51.0% used tooth brush to clean their mouths, 28.0% used chewing stick, 14.0% used only water to rinse their mouths, 4.0% used charcoal to clean their mouths, 2.0% used salt water to clean their mouths and only 1.0% used sand to clean the mouth which goes to show the extent of poor knowledge of oral health and oral hygiene practices and may explain further the presence of oral health problems being experienced among the elderly populace of this community. This agrees with the reports made by Sofola (2010) who said that: “when there is low oral health awareness, there is a direct effect on the illness seeking behaviour of the individual and population”.

The significant correlation between bleeding gums, toothache and oral sores may have been due to the occurrence of periodontal diseases which is capable of causing these oral health problems. This surely, can be attributed to the poor oral hygiene practices of the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study carried out in Ikibiri community Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria, there is the presence of oral health problems among the elderly populace of Ikibiri Community which require urgent steps and strategies to be put in place in order to reduce the occurrence of oral health problems and also promote the oral health status of the elderly populace in this community.

The following steps and strategies are thus recommended to be put in place to reduce the occurrence of these oral health problems. Viz:

1. Provision of dental health personnel and services at Ikibiri community, which would enable the elderly to have access to oral health services.
2. Oral health education programmes should be carried out from time to time not just in Ikibiri Community but also in other communities in different Local Government Areas in Bayelsa and in Nigeria as a whole in order to provide proper education to the elderly and the entire populace on oral health and oral health promotion.

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